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ANALYSIS OF BPMN BASED BUSINESS PROCESS MODELS

It is common for modern enterprises to create and maintain collections of business process models intended to represent, share, and reuse knowledge about organizational activities. For large and medium organizations such collections may contain hundreds or even thousands of business process models. Whereas enterprise architecture standard TOGAF (The Open Group Architecture Framework) provides framework of Architecture Repository as the collection of architectural artifacts to which business process models also belong [1]. Since the process model repository is required to maintain the correctness and consistency of its content, the problem of business process models correctness evaluation becomes relevant [2].

Hence, we have proposed a method of analysis of business process models designed using the BPMN (Business Process Model and Notation) standard [3]. We have selected BPMN according to the latest survey, in which it is declared as the most popular process modeling standard (64% of respondents used it) [4]. The method is based on the control flow design rules and common BPMN “anti-patterns” (undefined start/end events, missing gateways, control flow connectivity issues, etc.). Thus, BPMN business process model might contain missing start/end events and tasks, as well as invalid events, tasks, and gateways.

To demonstrate implementation of the proposed method, we used it to analyze 25 various business process models provided by business diagramming software vendors Conceptdraw, EDraw, and MyDraw on their websites. Obtained results (see figure 1) demonstrate that most common errors of business process modeling are invalid functions (72% of models) and invalid errors (28% of models).

Fig. 1. Most common errors of business process models

Therefore, there are 20 incorrect models among the set of 25 BPMN models: one model with 6 errors, 3 models with 5 errors, 4 models with 3 errors, 5 models with 2 errors, and 7 models with 1 error (see figure 2).

Fig. 2. Evaluation and analysis of business process models correctness

In order to validate proposed method, we have prepared and analyzed 24 sample business process models. With considering that 15 of these 24 models contain errors, we compared results obtained by using proposed method with results obtained by using well known methods of process models evaluation: density and connectivity analysis [5]. Comparison of the obtained results is shown in table 1.

Table 1. Comparison with existing methods

Method	Correct	Incorrect	Evaluation error
Density analysis	13	11	45,83%
Connectivity analysis	9	15	62,5%
Proposed method	17	7	29,17%

According to validation results shown in table 1, proposed method of business process model analysis is presumably more efficient than existing methods. Future work includes enhancement of the proposed method in order to improve precision and decrease evaluation errors.

References

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